

A Correlation Between Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons and the 2175-Angstrom Extinction Feature

Nicholas James, Charlie Conroy, Ben Johnson

Abstract

We constrain the strength of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) emission and the strength of the 2175-angstrom extinction feature for a sample of 44 nearby galaxies. The parameters of interest are constrained using stellar population synthesis models, fit to photometric spectral energy distributions using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithm. While the 2175-angstrom extinction feature is in general poorly constrained in our data set, analysis reveals a positive correlation between the strength of this extinction feature and the PAH fraction of a galaxy. This correlation suggests that PAHs could be the dust particle responsible for the 2175-angstrom feature, as has been previously theorized. However, further analysis will be necessary to determine whether another galaxy characteristic could cause the two parameters to covary.

1. Introduction

The existence of an excess in interstellar dust extinction around 2175 angstroms has been known for decades. Originally discovered by Stecher (1965), this extinction feature has been well-studied and characterized in the Milky Way and in nearby galaxies, through the observation of the reddening of individual stars. The feature is more difficult to characterize, however, in more distant galaxies (where individual stars cannot be resolved), as dust attenuation in galaxies is significantly more difficult to model than the extinction of light from individual stars, due to the complex star-dust geometry and the potential for the scattering of light both out of and into the line of sight. However, modeling can be used to obtain constraints on the strength of this extinction feature, as well as many other galaxy parameters; galaxy modeling has been used to determine that local starburst galaxies generally have a non-existent 2175-angstrom extinction feature (Calzetti 2001). While the shape and strength of the feature vary, it is nearly always found to be centered at 2175 angstroms (Derck and Massa 1986).

The existence of this feature in numerous galaxies naturally leads to the question of what component of the interstellar medium is causing the excess extinction. Studies have shown

that certain carbonaceous compounds, such as graphite, absorb radiation particularly strongly around this wavelength regime (Draine 2003). In particular, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons have been proposed as a likely culprit behind the extinction excess.

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are a subset of hydrocarbon molecules, characterized by aromatic rings of carbon surrounded by hydrogen atoms (Draine 2003). They are thought to be a ubiquitous component of the interstellar medium of galaxies, and are easily observed by their strong IR emission features, particularly at wavelengths of 3.3, 6.2, 7.7, 8.6, and 11.3 micrometers (Leger and Puget 1984).

Recently, Blasberger et al. (2016) have studied the spectra of nearby stars, seeking a correlation between PAH emission along the line of sight and extinction of stellar light around 2175 angstroms. They find no correlation between the strength of the PAH emission and 2175-angstrom extinction features; however, they do find that the two features demonstrate a correlated shift towards longer wavelengths in stars with an effective temperature below 14500 Kelvin. They cite this correlation as evidence that PAHs could be the cause of the mysterious 2175-angstrom extinction feature.

The goal of this paper is similar to that of Blasberger et al. (2016), but we utilize a significantly different data set. We use broadband photometry of a sample of 44 nearby galaxies to characterize the strength of PAH emission and 2175-angstrom extinction in each galaxy; a positive correlation between the strength of the two features would provide evidence that PAHs may be the cause of the extinction feature. To determine the strength of these features from our broadband spectral energy distributions, we use the Flexible Stellar Population Synthesis models of Conroy, Gunn, and White (2009), fit to our data using an implementation of the Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithm.

2. Data Set

Our data set consists of broadband photometry of 44 nearby galaxies from the ultraviolet through the infrared, compiled from the Spitzer Infrared Nearby Galaxies Survey (SINGS), the Key Insights on Nearby Galaxies: A Far-Infrared Survey with Herschel (KINGFISH) survey, the Local Volume Legacy (LVL) survey, and an SED atlas collected by Brown et al. (2014).

The SINGS survey (detailed in Kennicutt et al. 2003) is a photometric and spectroscopic infrared survey of 75 nearby galaxies, conducted using the Spitzer Space Telescope. In addition to photometry in the Spitzer IRAC and MIPS bands, supplementary aperture-matched photometry was obtained in the GALEX FUV and NUV, BVRI, and 2MASS JHK

bands (Dale et al. 2007). Dale et al. (2012) added to the breadth of this sample by obtaining Herschel PACS and SPIRE photometry for the 61 galaxies in the KINGFISH sample (57 of which are shared with SINGS). The SINGS/KINGFISH data used in this paper is reported in Dale et al. (2016, in prep.), who redid some of the photometry from Dale et al. (2007) and Dale et al. (2012) and corrected other issues with the data set.

The LVL survey, also conducted with the Spitzer Space Telescope, obtained PACs and MIPS photometry for a volume-limited sample of galaxies, out to 11 megaparsecs (Dale et al. 2009). Supplementary aperture-matched photometry was obtained in the 2MASS JHK (Dale et al. 2009), GALEX FUV and NUV (Lee et al. 2010), and UBVR and SDSS ugriz (Cook et al. 2014) filters. The LVL photometry used in this paper was compiled from these three papers.

Brown et al. (2014) compiled a spectral energy distribution (SED) atlas of 129 nearby galaxies, producing matched-aperture photometry of archival Swift, GALEX, SDSS, 2MASS, Spitzer, and WISE images. We make use of all but the WISE photometry. We additionally obtained Herschel photometry (courtesy of Ben Johnson) from KINGFISH images, using the same apertures as Brown et al. The Brown et al. atlas only extends through the Spitzer 24-micron filter in the infrared, so this Herschel data was vital for fully characterizing the dust content of the galaxies in the data set.

Additionally, Swift UVOT photometry, particularly in the M2 filter, was vital to our goal of probing the 2175-angstrom extinction feature. The Brown et al. (2014) sample contains such UVOT photometry for some galaxies, but it was necessary to obtain our own UVOT photometry for the galaxies in the SINGS/KINGFISH and LVL samples and those from Brown et al. (2014) that lacked UVOT photometry. We obtained UVOT W2, M2, and W1 images of 57 galaxies from Erik Hoversten, and used these to produce photometry aperture-matched to that from the SINGS/KINGFISH, LVL, and Brown et al. surveys.

In all, our sample totals 44 galaxies: those for which we have GALEX FUV and NUV photometry, Swift UVOT W2, M2, and W1 photometry, either SDSS ugriz or some subset of UBVR optical photometry, and adequate IR photometry (extending to at least 160 microns). Table 1 describes the wavelength coverage of each of the three data sets from which we compiled our photometry. For those galaxies that met these requirements in more than one of the data sets, we fit each available photometry set individually. Table 2 gives the number of galaxies in each data set, as well as the subset of those that are not shared with either of the other sets (for a list of each galaxy in our sample, and to determine which data sets it is contained in, one can consult Table 4).

All photometry was corrected for galactic extinction according to Schlafly and Finkbeiner (2011).

Table 1. Wavelength coverage for each data set

	Brown et al. (2014)	LVL	SINGS
GALEX FUV+NUV	Yes	Yes	Yes
Swift UVOT W2, M2, and W1	Yes	Yes*	Yes*
SDSS ugriz	Yes	Partial	Partial
UBVRI	No	Partial	Partial
2MASS JHK	Yes	Yes	Yes
Spitzer IRAC	Yes	Yes	Yes
Spitzer MIPS	Only 24 micron	Yes	Yes
Herschel PACS	Yes*	No	Yes
Herschel SPIRE	Yes*	No	Yes

Note. — “Yes” means that the given data set (Brown, LVL, or SINGS) contains photometry for each band in the corresponding category, while “no” means photometry was incomplete or absent within those bands. An asterisk marks those galaxies for which we had to produce our own UVOT or Herschel photometry, aperture-matched to the rest of the data set. The LVL and SINGS data sets contained both UBVRI and SDSS ugriz and optical photometry; we preferentially used the ugriz photometry when available. Additionally, the LVL data consisted of just UBVR, lacking I, while the SINGS data set consisted of just BVRI, lacking U. The Spitzer photometry in Brown et al. (2014) only extends to the 24 micron filter.

3. Model and Fitting

3.1. FSPS Model

We used the Flexible Stellar Population Synthesis (FSPS) models of Conroy, Gunn, and White (2009) to extract the dust emission and attenuation parameters of each galaxy in our sample from its broadband SED. FSPS uses the stellar population synthesis (SPS) technique to model a galaxy’s spectral energy distribution, allowing one to extract the galaxy’s physical parameters, such as mass, age, and metallicity, from SED data.

In stellar population synthesis, a galaxy is treated as a composite of simple stellar populations (SSPs), populations of stars of the same age and metallicity. The masses of the stars that make up the SSP are determined based on a stellar initial mass function; the temperature and surface gravity of each star, at the age of the SSP, can then be determined using stellar evolution model-based isochrones. The spectrum of each star (determined from the temperature, metallicity, and surface gravity using theoretical or empirical spectral libraries) is then integrated over, producing the overall SSP spectrum (Conroy 2013).

SSPs of differing ages are combined to form a composite stellar population (CSP), based on a model star formation history. Integrating over SSP spectra of different ages, weighted by the star formation history, and adding in a model for dust attenuation and emission, produces the spectrum of a galaxy.

3.2. Model Parameters

We will now briefly summarize the parameters and parameterizations that went into the FSPS (Conroy, Gunn, and White 2009) models that we fit to our data. The 11 parameters that were allowed to vary during the fitting process are listed in Table 3, along with the bounds for the (flat) priors set on these free parameters.

We parameterized the star formation history with a delayed tau model (star formation rate $\propto te^{-t/\tau}$). Both τ (units of Gyr, logarithmically sampled in the parameter $\log \tau$) and the galaxy’s age (t , units of Gyr) are free parameters. The stellar metallicity is specified by the free parameter Z (where Z is the percentage of the star by mass that is not helium or hydrogen), which varies logarithmically relative to the metallicity of the Sun as $\log Z/Z_{\odot}$. We make use of the Padova isochrones, the MILES empirical spectral library, and the initial mass function of Kroupa (2001).

Infrared dust emission was modeled based on Draine and Li (2007). Three free parameters,

U_{min} , γ , and q_{PAH} , go into the emission model. U_{min} specifies the minimum interstellar radiation field strength relative to that of the Milky Way, while γ specifies the relative contribution of dust heated by a radiation field at that minimum strength (i.e., in the general interstellar medium) and dust heated by a stronger field (i.e., around stars). q_{PAH} specifies the percentage of dust mass that is composed of PAHs; we were particularly interested in obtaining constraints on this parameter for the galaxies in our sample.

Dust attenuation is modeled based on the average Milky Way extinction curve, according to Cardelli et al. (1989). The extinction curve is parameterized based on the parameter

$$R_V \equiv \frac{A_V}{E(B - V)} \quad (1)$$

where A_V is the V-band extinction and $E(B - V)$ is the difference between B-band and V-band extinction. R_V is allowed to vary between 1-5, with 3.1 being the average value for the Milky Way.

Additionally, the 2175-angstrom extinction feature is added to the extinction curve through the UVB (“ultraviolet bump”) parameter. This parameter specifies the strength of the extinction feature relative to its average strength in the Milky Way, with a value of 1 implying the same strength as the Milky Way. This is the other parameter that we were particularly interested in constraining for the galaxies in our sample.

The free parameters Dust1 and Dust2 characterize the amount of dust in the galaxy. Dust1 represents dust around young stars, while Dust2 represents dust in the interstellar medium. Dust2 only attenuates the light of stars older than 10^7 years.

The final free parameter, galaxy mass (measured in solar masses), serves mainly as a scaling factor for the overall brightness of the SED.

3.3. MCMC Fitting

We used a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) fitting algorithm to fit the FSPS model to each galaxy in our data set. We made use of Prospector, a Python-based MCMC implementation developed for use with FSPS (Leja et al. 2016, Johnson et al. 2016). Each fit was run using 1054 MCMC walkers over 2048 iterations, after successive burn-in periods (after each of which the walkers were re-initialized around the highest probability walker) of 40, 40, 80, 80, 100, 200, 300, and 400 iterations.

Table 2. Galaxy Sample

	Total number of galaxies	Galaxies contained only in one data set
Brown et al. (2014)	8	3
LVL	28	18
SINGS	23	9

Note. — There are a total of 44 unique galaxies in our sample: the 30 galaxies (as listed in this table) that are only contained in one out of the three data sets, plus 14 that are contained in two or three of the data sets.

Table 3. Model Parameters

Parameter	Prior
Mass	$[10^5, 10^{13}]$
$\log Z/Z_\odot$	$[-1, 0.19]$
$\log \tau$	$[-1, 2]$
t	$[0.1, 14]$
Dust1	$[0, 2]$
Dust2	$[0, 2]$
UVB	$[0, 2]$
R_V	$[1, 5]$
U_{min}	$[0.1, 25]$
γ	$[0, 1]$
q_{PAH}	$[0, 10]$

Note. — Details on each of these parameters are provided in Section 3.2

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Fitting Results

Figure 1 displays the result from one of our fits—that of NGC 5866, using Brown et al. (2014) photometry. The full photometric SED is plotted against the best-fit model photometry and spectrum (where “best-fit” means the median of the marginalized posterior distribution is chosen for each parameter).

Figure 2 contains plots similar to Figure 1, but focusing in on the 2175-angstrom extinction feature and the region of PAH emission, for three different galaxies. The effect of PAH molecules on these galaxy SEDs is fairly evident by eye, as can be seen in the plots on the right. For NGC 5866, which has a PAH fraction of only $1.8 \pm 0.3\%$, there is little rise in the flux in the filters around 3-12 micrometers, where the PAH emission bands are located. In NGC 3344 however, for which the fit determined a PAH fraction of $3.6 \pm 0.5\%$, there is a significant rise in flux in this region; the flux is also significantly greater relative to the flux due to continuum dust emission (seen towards longer wavelengths) than it is for NGC 5866. A rise in flux due to PAHs can also be seen for NGC 3034, for which the fit determined a more moderate PAH fraction of $2.5 \pm 0.5\%$.

The effect of the 2175-angstrom extinction feature on the SEDs in the plots in the left of Figure 2 is significantly more subtle. The fit for NGC 3034 determined a relatively high strength for this feature, at 0.8 ± 0.1 relative to that of the Milky Way. This can be seen in the dip in the flux in the UVOT M2 filter (the third red data point in the bottom left plot). For NGC 5866 and NGC 3344, for which fitting determined a lower strength for the extinction feature (0.3 ± 0.2 and 0.2 ± 0.1 , respectively), this dip is not as evident, in particular for NGC 3344. However, the difference is subtle (in particular between NGC 5866 and NGC 3034). This is a factor of the small size of the 2175-angstrom extinction feature relative to the bandpasses of the UVOT and GALEX FUV filters in which it is contained, as well as the underlying dependence of the observed feature on the galaxy’s stellar flux.

Table 4 presents the median value of the marginalized posterior distributions for both the PAH fraction (q_{PAH}) and 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength (UVB) parameters for each galaxy in our sample, with one standard deviation errors. For galaxies for which we had data from multiple sources (LVL, SINGS, and/or Brown et al. 2014), we fit each of the available photometry sets separately. The median parameter values are generally in agreement, within the error bounds, for galaxies shared between the three sources.

Table 4. Median Parameter Values

	q_{PAH} (Brown)	UVB (Brown)	q_{PAH} (LVL)	UVB (LVL)	q_{PAH} (SINGS)	UVB (SINGS)
DDO 053					0.2±0.2	0.08±0.06
Holmberg I					0.3±0.2	1.0±0.7
Holmberg II					0.08±0.06	0.9±0.6
Markarian 33					1.3±0.3	0.7±0.3
NGC 0024			2.6±0.5	0.9±0.6	2.2±0.5	1.1±0.7
NGC 0337					2.4±0.3	0.2±0.2
NGC 0625			0.3±0.2	0.7±0.4		
NGC 0628	4.1±0.4	0.4±0.3	3.7±0.5	1.5±0.3	4.0±0.4	0.6±0.4
NGC 0855			2.4±0.4	0.3±0.2	2.0±0.4	0.8±0.5
NGC 0925					2.5±0.4	1.1±0.7
NGC 1266					0.2±0.1	0.06±0.04
NGC 1512			3.2±0.5	0.06±0.05		
NGC 1705			0.8±0.2	0.7±0.5		
NGC 1800			1.5±0.4	1.5±0.7		
NGC 2366			0.06±0.04	0.7±0.5		
NGC 2403			3.3±0.4	1.1±0.6	2.9±0.4	1.8±0.3
NGC 2798	1.7±0.2	0.5±0.1			2.1±0.3	0.5±0.1
NGC 2841					3.8±0.6	1.1±0.6
NGC 3031			3.1±0.7	1.5±0.6		
NGC 3034			2.4±0.7	0.7±0.1	2.5±0.6	0.8±0.1
NGC 3184					4.7±0.5	0.7±0.4
NGC 3239			1.0±0.2	0.9±0.6		
NGC 3344			3.6±0.5	0.2±0.1		
NGC 3351			2.7±0.5	0.2±0.2	2.6±0.4	0.2±0.1
NGC 3627			3.3±0.5	0.3±0.2	3.6±0.5	0.4±0.2
NGC 3628			3.5±0.5	0.9±0.4		
NGC 4236			0.8±0.3	1.1±0.7	0.8±0.4	0.9±0.6
NGC 4242			2.3±0.4	1.1±0.7		
NGC 4395			1.2±0.3	0.5±0.3		
NGC 4449			2.2±0.3	1.3±0.6		
NGC 4485			1.8±0.3	0.7±0.5		
NGC 4490			2.2±0.3	0.6±0.2		
NGC 4559	5.6±0.5	0.9±0.6			3.4±0.4	1.0±0.6
NGC 4579	2.1±0.5	0.6±0.4			2.9±0.6	0.6±0.4
NGC 4631	3.3±0.2	0.7±0.3				

Fig. 1.— The photometric data (from Brown et al. 2014) for NGC 5866 is plotted in red, alongside the best-fit model photometry (in blue) and spectrum (in green).

Fig. 2.— Here we focus in on two regions of the galaxy SEDs: the region containing the 2175-angstrom extinction feature (in the plots on the left), and the region containing PAH emission (in the plots on the right). The three galaxies are, from top to bottom, NGC 5866 (the entire SED of which is plotted in Figure 1), NGC 3344, and NGC 3034. NGC 5866 has a particularly low PAH fraction and 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength. NGC 3344 has a higher PAH fraction, but a low 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength. NGC 3034 has a particularly high value for the strength of the 2175-angstrom extinction feature, and a moderate PAH fraction. The effect of PAHs on the SED is easy to see by eye; the 2175-angstrom extinction feature, however, is much more subtle.

Table 4—Continued

	q_{PAH} (Brown)	UVB (Brown)	q_{PAH} (LVL)	UVB (LVL)	q_{PAH} (SINGS)	UVB (SINGS)
NGC 4826	2.8±0.4	0.2±0.1				
NGC 5194			3.9±0.5	0.5±0.2	4.1±0.4	1.0±0.3
NGC 5236			3.8±0.5	0.5±0.1		
NGC 5253			1.0±0.3	0.1±0.1		
NGC 5457			3.5±0.5	1.5±0.5	3.6±0.4	1.3±0.6
NGC 5866	1.8±0.3	0.3±0.2				
NGC 6503			3.8±0.5	0.8±0.3		
NGC 7090			2.8±0.4	0.7±0.2		
NGC 7331	3.5±0.4	0.1±0.1			4.0±0.4	0.5±0.2

Note. — isted values are the median of the marginalized posterior distribution for each parameter (after fitting of the specified data set), with 1σ errors

4.2. Analysis

The median parameter values for the PAH fraction and 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength are plotted against one another in Figure 3. For the galaxies contained in multiple data sets, we averaged together the median parameter values from the multiple fits.

Figure 3 shows no clear trend between the two parameters. However, it is important to note that there is a large amount of uncertainty in the best-fit 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength for many of the galaxies in our sample. This high level of uncertainty is likely due to the small size of the 2175-angstrom extinction feature relative to the filters in which it is contained, which results in its effect on the flux in these filters being small. Additionally, as can be seen in Figure 5, there are a number of galaxies in our sample for which the amount of dust in the galaxy (as specified by the Dust2 parameter) is particularly small; these galaxies tend to also have a poorly constrained UVB strength. This pattern is expected for galaxies with a low dust mass, as the 2175-angstrom extinction feature is parameterized relative to the rest of the extinction curve, as opposed to defining an absolute amount of extinction; thus, for galaxies with a small amount of dust, and thus a small amount of dust attenuation, it will be difficult to determine the strength of attenuation around 2175 angstroms relative to the small amount of attenuation that does exist.

In Figure 4, galaxies with an uncertainty in the 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength greater than 0.4 have been removed. The removal of these galaxies reveals a trend that was hidden by the poor constraints on UVB. A clear positive correlation can be seen between PAH fraction and 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength for this subset of galaxies. A linear least squares fit to the entire data set, with the UVB parameter values weighted by their inverse variance, determines a slope of 0.22 for this trend. This fit is plotted in both Figure 3 and Figure 4. Bootstrap resampling of the data set determines a standard deviation of 0.18 for the slope of the fit. Thus, the correlation between the two parameters may not be positive to a statistically significant extent; more careful determination of the slope and its error, as well as the addition of more galaxies with well-constrained 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength to the sample, will be important in order to better determine the strength and significance of the positive correlation.

This tentative correlation between PAH fraction and 2175-angstrom feature strength in our sample of nearby galaxies suggests that PAHs could be the cause of the extinction feature, as has been previously theorized. However, it is important to note that correlation does not necessarily imply causation, and there could potentially be other explanations behind the positive correlation between the two features. It is reasonable to expect that some other physical characteristic of a galaxy, such as metallicity or star formation rate, might have a positive correlation with both of the features, causing both to vary in the same manner even

Fig. 3.— The median parameter values for PAH fraction (q_{PAH}) and 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength (UVB) are plotted against one another (for those galaxies for which we had more than one set of data, the parameters returned by multiple fits are averaged together). The correlation between the two features is unclear in this plot, as it is obscured by the many galaxies that have a poorly constrained UVB strength. Also plotted is a linear least squares fit to the data (with the UVB values being weighted by $1/\sigma^2$), with a slope of 0.22 ± 0.18 .

Fig. 4.— The same as Figure 4, except galaxies with an uncertainty in the UVB strength greater than 0.4 have been removed. A positive correlation between PAH fraction and 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength becomes more clear once these poorly constrained galaxies are removed. The linear fit follows this trend fairly closely (note that the fit is to the entire galaxy set, as in figure 3); a significant number of galaxies fall below the line, however. (Note: the choice of 0.4 as the cutoff uncertainty is fairly arbitrary. In general, the smaller the cutoff uncertainty, the more linear the correlation between the two parameters becomes)

Fig. 5.— The median Dust2 parameter values (specifying the amount of dust in the galaxy) for each galaxy are plotted along the x-axis, vs. the error in the 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength for each galaxy along the y-axis. An anticorrelation can be seen between the amount of dust in a galaxy and the error in the UVB strength determined by the fits.

if a different component of the dust population is the true culprit behind the 2175-angstrom feature.

As a preliminary investigation of this possibility, we have color-coded our PAH fraction vs. UVB strength plots based on four different galaxy parameters (Figure 6). In the upper left of Figure 6, the data points are color coded-based on stellar metallicity ($\log Z/Z_{\odot}$), while the data points in the upper right are color-coded based on the logarithm of the amount of dust in the galaxy ($\log \text{Dust}_2$). The data points in the lower left are color-coded based on specific star formation rate (star formation rate in stellar mass per year divided by total galaxy stellar mass). There is no clear pattern in the coloration in any of these plots, suggesting that PAH fraction and UVB strength do not covary with either metallicity, total dust content, or specific star formation rate for the galaxies in our sample. More concrete analysis, preferably with a larger data set, will be needed to more firmly establish whether or not these physical parameters, or others, could cause PAH fraction and UVB strength to covary.

One other notable feature of Figure 4 is the large number of galaxies that lie below the linear trend, with comparatively few lying above it. This behavior could potentially be explained, even in the presence of a generally positive correlation between PAHs and the 2175-angstrom extinction feature, if there were some other external factor that acted to dampen the strength of the extinction feature, without affecting the PAH emission. Effects of the star-dust geometry, or radiative transfer effects, could potentially act to dampen the extinction feature (Witt and Gordon 2000), but would have less effect on the strength of PAH emission features. As a simple test for geometric effects, the lower right plot of Figure 6 color-codes the data points by the ratio between the minor axis and major axis of each galaxy. No clear trend based on this ratio can be seen.

5. Conclusion and Future Direction

We find a positive correlation between the PAH fraction and 2175-angstrom extinction feature strength in a sample of 44 nearby galaxies. This correlation suggests that PAHs could be the cause of this extinction feature, as has been previously theorized. However, it is important to keep in mind that this correlation does not necessarily imply causation. In future analysis, it will be important to further investigate the other galaxy characteristics that could potentially cause these two features to covary, such as metallicity or star formation rate. Adding additional galaxies to our data set would allow us to better determine the effects of these additional parameters, and whether or not PAHs do correlate with the extinction feature when all else is held equal; in addition, additional data, in which the 2175-

Fig. 6.— Each of these four plots contains the trimmed data set and linear fit from Figure 4, except the data points have been color-coded by a different galaxy parameter in each plot. Upper left: data points are color-coded by stellar metallicity ($\log Z/Z_{\odot}$). Upper right: data points are color-coded by the logarithm of the galaxy dust content ($\log \text{Dust2}$). Lower left: data points are color-coded by the logarithm of the specific star formation rate. Lower right: data points are color-coded by the ratio between the minor and major axis of each galaxy (estimated using the ratio of the photometric apertures). No clear trend can be seen in any of these four coloration schemes.

angstrom extinction feature is well constrained, will be important for better determining the strength of the positive correlation between PAHs and the extinction feature.

6. Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Erik Hoversten for the use of his Swift UVOT images, Daniel Dale and Michael Brown for consultation about their data sets, and Joel Leja for advice on certain aspects of the data set.

7. References

- Blasberger, E. et al. 2016, ArXiv e-prints
- Brown, M. J. et al. 2014, ApJ, 212, 18
- Cardelli, J. A. et al. 1989, ApJ, 345, 245
- Calzetti, D. 2001, Astronomical Society of the Pacific, 113, 1449
- Conroy, C., Gunn, J. E., and White, M. 2009, ApJ, 699, 486
- Conroy, C. and Gunn, J. E. 2010, ApJ, 712, 833
- Conroy, C. 2013, Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics, 51, 393
- Cook, D. O. Cook et al. 2014, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society, 445, 881
- Dale, D. A. et al. 2007, ApJ, 655, 863
- Dale, D. A. et al. 2009, ApJ, 703, 517
- Dale, D. A. et al. 2012, ApJ, 145, 95
- Dale, D. A. et al. 2016 (in prep.)
- Draine, B. T. 2003, Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics, 41, 241
- Draine, B. T. and Li, A. 2007, ApJ, 657, 810
- Foreman-Mackey, D. et al. 2012, The Astronomical Society of the Pacific, 125, 925
- Johnson, B. D. et al. 2016 (in prep.)
- Lee, J. C. et al. 2011, ApJ, 192, 6
- Leger, A. and Puget, J. L. 1984, Astronomy and Astrophysics, 137
- Leja, J. L. et al. 2016, ArXiv e-prints
- Kennicutt, R. C. et al. 2003, Publication of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific, 115, 928
- Massa, D. and Fitzpatrick, E. L. 1986, ApJ, 60, 305
- Schlafly, E. F. and Finkbeiner, D. P. 2011, ApJ, 737, 103
- Stecher, T. P. 1965, ApJ, 142, 1683
- Witt, A. N. and Gordon, K. D. 2000, ApJ, 528, 799